

A blockchain-based electronic voting system without third parties

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Abstract: Voting is one of the fundamental pillars of modern democracy. Continuous efforts have been made to strengthen the processes and methods involved to achieve verifiable, transparent voting systems. In recent years, block chain has been increasingly used to address multi-dimensional challenges across widespread application domains including healthcare, finance and e-voting. However, achieving an efficient solution via use of block chain requires consideration of a range of factors such as block generation rate, transaction speed, and block size which have a profound role in determining the overall performance of the solution. Current research into this aspect of block chain is focused on Bit coin with the objective to achieve comparable performance as of existing online payment systems such as VISA. However, there exists a gap in literature with respect to investigating performance constraints for wider application domains. In this paper, we present our efforts to address this gap by presenting a detailed study into performance and scalability constraints for an e-voting system. Specifically, we conducted rigorous experimentation with permissioned and permission less block chain settings across different scenarios with respect to voting population, block size, block generation rate and transaction speed. The experiments highlighted interesting observations with respect to the impact of these parameters on the overall efficiency and scalability of the e-voting model including trade-offs between different parameters as well as security and performance.

Keywords: Block Chain, Electronic Voting System

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Accepted: 17 May, 2022; **Published:** 31 May, 2022

How to cite this article: Islam Khandaker Sajidul, Jungang Lou (2022). A blockchain-based electronic voting system without third parties.

North American Academic Research, 5(5), 58-69. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6600587>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Voting is one of the fundamental characteristics of human democracy with continuous efforts made throughout human history to improve the processes, mechanisms and methods involved to conduct voting in a verifiable, transparent and accessible manner. The advent of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), has brought renewed emphasis on using ICT to facilitate voting processes primarily to enable transparency and accessibility. Since its first use as punched-card ballots in 1960s, e-voting systems have achieved remarkable progress with its adaptation using the internet technologies [1] with a range of terminologies used such as e-voting (using a machine in a polling station), digital voting (use of electronic devices such as voting machines) and i-voting (using web browser to cast vote). The focus of our research is on using advancements in ICT via electronic machines in polling stations as part of a public vote

(commonly called General Election) with the view of investigating challenges in this respect and potential solutions to address them. Blockchain has attracted significant attention with prominent applications across finance [2], healthcare [3] and supply chain management systems [4]. A Blockchain resembles a data structure which maintains and shares all the transactions being executed through its genesis. It is primarily a distributed decentralized database that maintains a complete list of constantly germinating and growing data records secured from unauthorized manipulation, tampering and revision. Blockchain allows every user to connect to the network, send new transactions to it, verify transactions and create new blocks [5, 6, 7]. Each block is assigned a cryptographic hash (which may also be treated as a fingerprint of the block) that remains valid as long as the data in the block is not altered. If any changes are made in the block, the cryptographic hash would change immediately indicating the change in the data which may be due to a malicious activity. Therefore, due to its strong foundations in cryptography, blockchain has been increasingly used to mitigate against unauthorized transactions across various domains [7, 8, 9].

2. Electronic Voting

Electronic voting has been an area of research focus for many years by using computing machines and equipment to cast votes and produce high quality and precise results in accordance with the sentiments of the participating voters. Various attempts have been adopted in practice to support election process through the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). One of the first uses of technology involved casting vote on paper which were scanned and tallied at every polling cell on a central server [20, 21]. Direct Recording Electronic (DRE) voting systems were adopted later and have attracted significant success in encouraging voters to use this technology. In the case of DRE, voters begin their journey by going to their polling place and get their token to vote where they utilize their token at the voting terminal to vote for their preferred candidate. When the candidate selection procedure is completed, DRE systems present the final selection to the voter before ballot casting is completed [22].

More recently, Hao et al. [21] proposed a two round protocol that computes the tally in two rounds without using a private channel or a trusted third party. The protocol is efficient in terms of computation and bandwidth consumption but is neither robust nor fair in certain conditions [22]. Dalia et al. [22] proposed a protocol to improve the robustness and fairness of the two round protocol. Shahandashti et al. [23] proposed E2E verifiable voting system named DRE-ip (DRE-i with enhanced privacy), that overcomes limitations of DRE-i [24] i.e. instead of pre-computing ciphertexts, DRE-ip encrypts the vote on the fly during voting process. DRE-ip achieves E2E verifiability without TAs, but at the same time provides a significantly stronger privacy guarantee than DREi. In [25], end-to-end verifiability is achieved through the Mixnet protocol [26] that recovers the plaintext ballot in an unlinkable manner by randomizing the ciphertext through a chain of mix servers. These approaches perform well for end-to-end verifiability without compromising the privacy of voters.

3. Blockchain-Based Voting System

In every democracy, the security of an election is a matter of national security. The computer security field has for a decade studied the possibilities of electronic voting systems, intending to minimize the cost of having a national election, while fulfilling and increasing the security conditions of an election. From the dawn of democratically electing candidates, the voting system has been based on pen and paper. Replacing the traditional pen and paper scheme with

a new election system is critical to limit fraud and having the voting process traceable and verifiable. A blockchain is a distributed, immutable, incontrovertible, public ledger. This new technology works through four main features:

1. The ledger exists in many different locations: No single point of failure in the maintenance of the distributed ledger.
2. There is distributed control over who can append new transactions to the ledger.
3. Any proposed "new block" to the ledger must reference the previous version of the ledger, creating an immutable chain from where the blockchain gets its name and thus preventing tampering with the integrity of previous entries.
4. A majority of the network nodes must reach a consensus before a proposed new block of entries becomes a permanent part of the ledger.

In a blockchain-based e-voting system, the following key roles would be identified:

1. Election administrators: Manage the lifecycle of an election. Multiple trusted institutions and companies are enrolled in this role. The election administrators specify the election type and create the aforementioned election, configure ballots, register voters, decide the lifetime of the election and assign permissioned nodes.
2. Voters: For elections to which they are eligible for, voters can authenticate themselves, load election ballots, cast their vote, and verify their vote after an election is over. Voters can be rewarded for voting with tokens when they cast their vote in an election in the near future, which could be integrated with a smart city project.
3. District nodes: When the election administrators create an election, each ballot smart contracts, representing each voting district, are deployed onto the blockchain. When the ballot smart contracts are created, each of the corresponding district nodes is permitted to interact with their corresponding ballot smart contract. When an individual voter casts his vote from his corresponding smart contract, the vote data is verified by all of the corresponding district nodes, and every vote they agree on is appended onto the blockchain when block time has been reached.
4. Bootnodes: Each institution, with permissioned access to the network, hosts a boot node. A boot node helps the district nodes to discover each other and communicate. The boot nodes do not keep any state of the blockchain and are ran on a static IP so that district nodes find their peers faster.

3.1. The benefits of Blockchain-based Voting System

The ultimate goal for building a blockchain-based voting system is to provide an accessible, secure, transparent and verifiable election process. Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology make it possible to overcome corruption and be tamper-proof because data is protected by cryptography, hence immutable. In the digital world, mobile technology can help participants cast their votes through mobile devices, making it easier for people with disabilities, military overseas, or simply any voter, to participate in elections. Anyone participating in the election can verify that they have voted for their intended candidate by encrypting/ decrypting the vote they have casted. The process is auditable and external observers can verify results end-to-end by taking a look at the blockchain data and counting the public results by themselves.

3.2 The key technological approaches:

A blockchain-based voting system can run on a permissioned blockchain. This means that the company developing the system has their own ledger, token, and set of rules in order to conduct the election. The organizer needs to create the contents and rules for defining the elections. A token can be used as a representation of a vote. With the use of digital signatures, signing of messages with cryptography and smart contracts, tokens can be sent securely to a person’s address representing one vote.

To process transactions in the permissioned blockchain, trusted consensus nodes can be used and paid with the native token using a Proof-of-Stake consensus mechanism. Any external observer inside or outside of the jurisdiction of the election authority can use auditor nodes to access the blockchain and verify the voting process and results end-to-end. There are several startups working on solutions for blockchain-based voting systems such as Vote and Agora. Votem has published a “Proof of Vote” whitepaper in which they describe the use of technologies such as ElGamal re-encryption mixnet for anonymity, private key generation and hashing using SHA256. The voting company also uses the Proof-of-Authority consensus approach meaning that nodes are assigned permissions as validators to run on the network and to put transactions in blocks. Furthermore, it describes the authentication and authorization processes, once the electoral authority provides the identification of eligible voters.

Agora has developed an innovative voting implementation with layers for building a voting system. Its architecture is conformed by five layers: the Bulletin Board blockchain, Cotena, the Bitcoin blockchain, the Valeda network and Votapp.

Private blockchains and side chains are used to interact Between them and the Bitcoin blockchain to make Voting transactions secure in the network. Votapp is the application connected to the Agora’s network by which voters can vote through their **mobile phones**.

3.3 Blockchain Voting Makes Democracy More Transparent:

There’s a reason why we have to go to a polling place to fill out ballots for our elections. Anonymous ballots are the easiest way to protect the integrity of the vote while also protecting voter privacy at the same time in Fig. 1 shown. Digital voting has been a difficult challenge because it’s tough to verify that each ballot is valid while also keeping them anonymous. Blockchain voting could change that with its cryptography.

Fig. 1. Blockchain-based e-voting transparent system.

4. Verifying Voter Identity:

If that first explanation sounded simple and you wonder why we’re not voting on the blockchain already, just hold on. It’s actually a lot more complicated than that. There are a lot of issues that need a resolution first.

One major issue is verifying voter identity. In order for blockchain voting to work, we need a system that prevents people from voting more than once or voting in an election where they’re not a citizen. That get’s tricky on the blockchain because it relies on a central authority to verify citizenship or residency documentation.

A blockchain solution would likely rely on submitting passport or driver’s license scans. Then that identity might be connected with a mobile device via a password and two-factor authentication or biometrics (like a fingerprint). The idea is to verify that the person who submitted the citizenship documents is the same person who is actively at the computer or smartphone at the time of the vote.

Fig. 2. Verifying voter identity.

5. Maintaining Anonymity & the Secret Ballot:

Once we’ve verified identity and eligibility to vote, however, we need to separate it from the ballot itself. Importantly, one of the key parts of democracy is the secret ballot. Nobody should know how you voted so they can’t influence your vote in any way.

With blockchain voting, the information that registers on the blockchain shouldn’t include identifiable information. This means that information about the sender of the voting token has to be hidden. There are different ways to accomplish this, including zero-knowledge proofs, ring transactions, or various encryption methods. Each has its benefits, drawbacks, and technical challenges. True anonymity at the same time as verified identity is the big challenge of blockchain voting.

Cybersecurity experts generally agree that blockchains are unhackable (with the right network size and consensus algorithm). Logic proofs and statistics indicate that it becomes increasingly unlikely that a block can be compromised once the network confirms it. However, the anonymity needed for voting is more difficult to secure and be certain that it won’t be compromised. **‘Ballot request’** Once the identification process is complete and the authorization for the

participant is granted, an unmarked ballot is returned to the user's device from a trusted node to the eligible voter to prepare for voting.

6. Solution design for blockchain-based voting

Election setup: The election authority creates and defines the contents and rules of the voting process. Organizations and governments specify their election parameters to establish ground rules. Nodes are configured and added to the network using a Proof-of-Authority mechanism to designate identified trusted computers and a Proof-of-Stake approach to pay nodes in native Currency.

Private key generation: Trusted nodes in the private blockchain are assigned a private key portion. Multiple private keys from nodes altogether constitutes the private key for the election. No single node has the power to control the election's private key.

Voter pseudonym: Voters use their mobile device to generate a one-time pseudonym address to use it as identification in the blockchain. No viewer knows the link between the pseudonym and the identity of the voter.

Authentication: It is the responsibility of the election authority to identify the eligibility of participants in the election. For governmental elections, the department of motor vehicles, passport offices, or other governmental entities can handle this process. They authenticate the identity of a person and return a cryptographic signature of the voter's pseudonym as recognition of the identification.

Authorization. The voter sends his identifying data to an authorized entity assigned by the election authority. Validation of authentication is performed and also the voter's identity is checked to match which election ballot he was assigned to.

Ballot request: Once the identification process is complete and the authorization for the participant is granted, an unmarked ballot is returned to the user's device from a trusted node to the eligible voter to prepare for voting.

Voting: Using their mobile device, voters can mark their selection in a user-friendly interface connected to the private blockchain network.

Vote encryption: The vote is secured and encrypted by the user's device using ElGamal and zero-knowledge proof to protect it before entering the network. With a Benaloh Challenge, the voter can audit the encrypted vote prior to submission and verify that his or her intended vote is correct. Voters can see their vote was cast as intended in the ballot and can also discover dishonest voting applications.

Vote submission: The voter's device creates a transaction containing the pseudonym, the ballot, the zero-knowledge proof of the selection and the signature of the voter, and it is sent to the blockchain. Once the transaction is confirmed, the voter has performed the process of casting a vote.

End of voting: When the time has expired, as decided by the election authority, organizers execute an end of voting transaction to finalize the voting process. After that transaction no more votes are allowed.

Tally: After executing the end of voting transaction, the votes are decrypted by all nodes securely and the results counted. Anybody with an Auditor node can do an end to-end verification of the whole voting process. Authorities and external observers are able to count results independently by downloading all the transactions of the blockchain.

Then the Despite Security concerns, some still believe that blockchain-based voting systems will be leveraged in major elections moving forward. 'Maxim Rukinov', head of the Distributed Ledger Technologies Center of 'St. Petersburg

State University, told Cointelegraph that blockchain allows for a system of fair elections to take place within a trusted environment between participants who generally do not trust each other: "With blockchain, you can make voting available and increase the transparency of any election. In a perfect scenario, the results of such a vote cannot be faked."

Rukinov shared that he has been working with a team of researchers to develop an online voting system specifically designed for enterprise use. Known as "CryptoVeche," Rukinov explained that this particular system stores voting results in a blockchain, which is a type of distributed ledger. As such, the system is highly secure against external and internal hacks.

Alex Tapscott, the co-founder of the Blockchain Research Institute and a book author, explained this in detail for a New York Times article published in 2018, even before the COVID-19 pandemic brought new challenges to light. **Tapscott** pointed out that in elections, trust is concentrated within government agencies, which are extremely vulnerable to hacks, fraud, and human errors. To put this into perspective, a study released last year shows that local and federal government entities have fallen victim to 443 data breaches since 2014, but those mostly included lost hardware, mailing errors, and paper breaches.

Tapscott noted that a blockchain system relies on distributed network computers to verify transactions. Once verified, results are recorded in blocks that are linked cryptographically to the preceding block. A secure ledger is then formed, which is transparent to all network participants, yet remains immutable and tamper-proof. This feature is also important for ensuring that individuals only cast a single vote, as blockchain-based systems are meant to prevent double-spending.

7. Technical challenges must be overcome:

Of course, there is no denying that technical challenges related to blockchain-based voting systems remain. In addition to the security concerns mentioned by MIT researchers in their recent report, Rukinov acknowledged that developing an online voting system is challenging. Rukinov further explained that with blockchain systems the accuracy of transactions, in this case, voter registration is verified by a consensus mechanism between different members of the network. However, when it comes to voting systems independent observers must also be one of the parties involved with the consensus, meaning they would have to hold several validation nodes.

According to Rukinov, in most cases, the number of nodes owned by the network organizer is greater than the number of independent nodes. So in the case of a blockchain-based voting system, an attack may occur when those who control more than half of the resources can change data at random. Rukinov pointed out that this problem is not the case for all types of consensus mechanisms.

Lior Lamash, Founder and CEO of GK8, a cybersecurity company, also told Cointelegraph that while the immutable nature of blockchain makes it an effective platform to ensure the integrity of the voting process, several vulnerabilities remain. Specifically speaking, Lamash noted that voter identification is problematic when using blockchain-based voting systems:

"The security aspect of blockchain-based voting is tricky. On one hand, the blockchain itself is completely secured from even state-level hackers, as it employs hundreds of thousands of nodes on multiple servers across the globe. The challenge would be in securing the 'endpoints' of this network – individual ballots and voting stations."

Moreover, Lamash noted that while each ballot stores a user's private keys, a hacker could obtain that information and manipulate the entire election process: "This issue is quite similar to the challenge that banks and other financial institutions face when offering blockchain-based services."

Conclusion

With blockchain technology, voting is more sophisticated and reliable. With its built-in cryptographic network and secure algorithms, distributed ledger technology can successfully be the platform of a new voting system. The underlying technology of the system can ensure a completely tamper-proof voting process, which observers can audit it end-to-end. Despite this potential however, the majority of people still need to understand and trust the technology. Few governments have yet to consider implementing it. Nonetheless, blockchain has the potential to satisfy different issues that democratic communities have demanded for years. Blockchain voting still isn't perfect or ready for primetime yet. However, it's likely to be a massive change in democracy once it does reach legitimacy. Making voting easier and more transparent will create a more engaged electorate. It may also remind us of why representatives exist to think about policy full time and make wise decisions about things the general public might not be able to research fully. There are several organizations currently exploring voting on the blockchain. Easier voting could mean more frequent representative elections or ongoing referendums on our leadership. Even that would be a big change for democracy.

Author Contributions: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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